

MICRO-SKILLS OF SPEAKING SKILLS: A GLANCE ON FEATURES OF SPEAKING SKILLS

Uzbekistan State World Languages University,
English Language Integrated Courses no 1. Department
Teacher Uralov Islom Ural o'g'li
e-mail: islomuralov93@gmail.com

Abstract

All of the 4 skills possess distinctive features which is relevant to teaching learning process, including speaking skills. Speaking skills besides its components possess micro-skills as well. In this article generally speaking skills and micro-skills are described for the readers of the field.

Key words: *speaking skills, micro-skills, teaching speaking*

Along with other skills speaking skills play crucial role in learning language that helps to develop learners' productive skills. There are several components that speaking skills include which are considered to be its typical parts, however, this skill has micro-skills also which makes it accurate. In this article professionals of this field will be given information about these micro-skills that they will probably find useful.

According to Brown, speaking is a productive skill that can be directly and empirically observed. Speaking involves two people who are engaged in talking to each other. Then, Thornburry, points out that speaking is a part of daily life and the average person produces thousands of words in a day. From those definitions, it can be inferred that speaking is one of the most important skills that people should acquire well. People speak every time they need, every time they want something, every time they want to socialize, and they assess their progress in terms of their accomplishments in spoken communication.

Then, Harmer points out that the speakers of English, especially where it is a second language, will have to be able to use a range of conversational and conversational repair strategies. There are two purposes for people to speak to others. Firstly, they want to convey information and facilitating of goods and services. Secondly, they want to maintain and sustain good relations between people. The former purpose is usually called a transactional function and the latter is called an interpersonal function. The Micro Skills of Speaking has some micro skills as stated by Brown:

1. Produce differences among English phonemes and allophonic variants.
2. Produce chunks of language of different lengths.
3. Produce English stress patterns, words in stressed and unstressed positions, rhythmic structure, and intonation contours.
4. Produce reduced forms of words and phrases.
5. Use an adequate number of lexical units (words) to accomplish pragmatic purposes.
6. Produce fluent speech at different rates of delivery.
7. Monitor one's own oral production and use various strategic devices.
8. Use grammatical word classes, systems, word order, patterns, etc.
9. Produce speech in natural constituents.
10. Express particular meaning in different grammatical forms.

11. Use cohesive devices in spoken discourse.

The speaking micro skills above give us a description of what aspects of speaking skill that should be acquired in order to communicate well. There are some important micro skills that will determine the success of delivering message in the speaking, such as speaking fluently, accurately, and appropriately. From the description above, it can be inferred that in order to communicate well, the students have to acquire the micro skills underlying their speaking proficiencies.

Teaching speaking is more than teaching grammar and vocabulary. Teaching speaking involves both a command of certain skills and different types of knowledge. To teach speaking, a teacher should have some areas of knowledge. The knowledge is categorized as linguistic knowledge and extra-linguistic knowledge. The linguistic knowledge covers the genre knowledge, discourse, pragmatic, grammar, vocabulary and phonology while extra-linguistic knowledge covers the sociocultural knowledge. It is essential that a speaker should have those kinds of knowledge such as the knowledge of using the right words in the right order with the correct pronunciation, grammar, and vocabulary, the knowledge of knowing when clarity of message is essential and when precise understanding is not required and the knowledge of social and cultural rules and norms such as turn-taking, rate of speech, length of pauses between speakers, relative roles of participants i.e. understanding how to take into account who is speaking to whom, in what circumstances, about what, and for what reason. In summary, in order to learn speaking skills learners needs to learn main components of this skill however, they need to learn micro-skills of speaking skills in order to be aware of, to acquire the skills as well as to make it accurate, fluent and produce efficient speech.

Reference:

1. Desingning English Learning Materials for English Conversation Club in SMA N 1 Kroya